

Mosquito collection and handling protocol to obtain High-Molecular Weight DNA.

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Intended use: Genomic sequencing (WGS, long-read, Hi-C, etc.)

Target organisms: Arthropods (mosquitoes; Diptera: Culicidae)

Estimated duration: Field (3-24 h), Lab (2–3 h)

Skill level: Intermediate

Biosafety level: BSL-1 (if applicable)

This protocol details a procedure for the capture, handling and cryogenic preservation of mosquito specimens intended for use in genomic studies. The main goal of the protocol is to mitigate DNA degradation by nuclease activity by strictly avoiding freeze-thaw cycles. Due to small specimen size, it becomes essential to reduce DNA degradation, especially when the specimens are intended to be used for high-molecular weight DNA extraction.

To maintain the quality and integrity of genetic material samples should ideally be identified and stored on the same day of collection. When traps operate continuously for up to 24 h, the maximum elapsed time between trap deployment and specimen preservation should not exceed 48 h. This will prevent prolonged exposure of the genetic material to ambient conditions. For this reason, preliminary fieldwork planning and estimation of workload becomes essential.

Materials and equipment:

- BG-Sentinel 2 mosquito traps (Biogents AG, Ratisbona, Germany).
- 12 V battery (minimum 13 Ah) Solid Carbon dioxide (CO₂; commonly known as dry ice).
- Insulated polystyrene boxes (various sizes for field deployment and laboratory processing)
- Plexiglass tube to be used as a CO₂ delivery conduct.
- Sterile petri plates
- RNase-free, DNase-free microcentrifuge tubes (1.5mL or 2.0mL)
- Stereomicroscope
- fine-tipped and blunt-tipped forceps
- Shaved ice (H₂O) or a chill table.

Procedure:

1- Select an optimal location for the trap

Trap location is a critical component of the trapping procedure and should be selected according to the sampling objectives, target species, site security, and logistical accessibility. Some general recommendations are placing traps in areas of easy access, leveled ground and under vegetation cover that protects them from wind or direct sunlight, which can reduce the success of mosquito capture or reduce their survival once inside the trap (Figure 1). More details on trap location can be found in Figuerola *et al.* (2024).

Figure 1: Example of appropriate placements for BG-Sentinel 2 traps, with vegetation cover and leveled ground with no flooding risk.

- 2- **Trap setup:** Place trap on the floor in the selected location. It is recommended to place the 12V battery inside the trap to protect it from climatic conditions and from being accessed by animals (Figure 2a). Connect the battery to the mounting cables. Place the catch bag and the suction funnel (Figure 2b). In order to identify captures in future steps, place a small paper note inside the catch bag indicating place and date of capture, as well as operator, in case there is more than one collector working in the project (Figure 2b).

Figure 2: BG-Sentinel 2 set up: a) Battery placed inside the trap. b) Catch bag with an identifier label attached to the suction funnel.

- 3- **CO₂ baiting system setup:** Place approximately 1 kg of dry ice inside an insulated polystyrene box (Figure 3a). Use always a shovel to handle the dry ice in order to avoid injuries. The lid should fit tightly in the box. In case it does not, place some weight over the lid (e.g., rocks) to avoid it from falling because of wind, animals or CO₂ pressure itself (Figure 3b). Connect the CO₂ conduct from an exhaust in the top of the box lid directly to the entrance of the suction funnel (Figure 3b). This will allow to use the sublimating CO₂ as an attractant for mosquitoes. BG sentinel traps usually come with their own mosquito attractant (BG lure), but we recommend the use of CO₂ as attractant because it attracts all the mosquitoes, independently of their feeding preference, while mammophilic mosquitoes are more attracted to BG lure than ornithophilic species.

Figure 3: CO₂ baiting system. a) Polystyrene box (1) with dry ice and its fitting lid (2). b) Final trap set-up. The box of dry ice (3) is connected to the suction funnel (4) and a rock has been placed to ensure the lid stays in place.

- 4- **Trap operation:** Trap time operation can be adjusted according to mosquito abundance and climatic conditions. To optimize mosquito capture, trapping time should include most active hours of mosquitoes (for *Culex* usually during dawn and sunset). If needed, trap operation can be extended to a maximum of 24h. The dry ice and battery will last long enough to maintain the trap operating during that time. Mosquitoes usually survive inside the trap during that time period, but some may still die if the catch bag gets too full or the temperatures are extremely high. This would cause DNA degradation to begin and could negatively affect the recovery of high-molecular weight DNA, so shorter capture periods may be recommended if the conditions allow it.

- 5- **Mosquito collection and preservation:** When collecting the mosquitoes, remove the funnel without removing the catch bag from the ventilator's suction area. This will allow to close and secure the bag without risk of mosquitoes' escaping. Transfer the catch bag with the mosquitoes to an empty, separate polystyrene box for the transport back to the laboratory. At this point, the protocol can follow two different approaches:
 - a. Place the catch bag inside a polystyrene box with dry ice to kill the mosquitoes *in situ* and preserve them during transport to the laboratory. This method may create challenges for subsequent DNA extraction, such as lower DNA concentrations or increased fragmentation due to partial thawing during mosquito identification. However, it is the recommended approach in areas where mosquito-borne pathogen circulation has been confirmed or is suspected. Additionally, when trapping involves long

distances or extended transport times, this method helps reduce mosquito movement within the collection bag, thereby preventing the loss of body parts (e.g., setae or scales) which are often important for species identification.

- b. When conditions allow (e.g., no regulatory restrictions, no confirmed pathogen circulation, and short transport times), place the catch bag inside a polystyrene box without dry ice. Maintain the box closed, inside the vehicle at cool and stable temperatures, avoiding direct sunlight and overheating. This approach keeps mosquitoes alive during transport, preventing premature death prior to arrival to laboratory, when they must undergo anesthesia. This approach minimizes DNA degradation and avoids freeze–thaw cycles, thereby improving the recovery of high-molecular-weight DNA during extraction.

When using approach (a), steps 6 and 7 can be skipped, and samples can be processed directly for identification (step 8). In contrast, when using approach (b), proceed with anesthesia (6 and 7) before continuing to identification (step 8).

- 6- **CO₂ anesthesia:** Once in the laboratory, transfer catch bags containing the captures inside a new polystyrene box filled with dry ice to approximately half of its capacity. Place a layer of insulating material between the net and the dry ice (e.g., several pieces of cardboard or plastic boxes, Figure 4) to prevent direct contact. This ensures that mosquitoes are only exposed to gaseous CO₂ and avoids flash-freezing. Close the box lid securely and maintain CO₂ exposure until complete cessation of movement is observed. This step may take several minutes. Specimens should be checked regularly to confirm full anesthesia while minimizing exposure to low temperatures. Before transferring mosquitoes to Petri dishes, gently move the collection bag to verify that all individuals are immobilized.

It is possible that some mosquitoes may not be anesthetized but instead die from asphyxiation during the process. This does not represent a significant issue as freeze-thaw-induced DNA fragmentation is still avoided. In addition, although some DNA degradation may start after death, the identification process is typically not long enough to substantially affect downstream DNA extraction. When in doubt, it is preferable to expose the mosquitoes to CO₂ for a longer time, even at the risk of some mortality, rather than underexpose the specimens and be forced to repeat the process because the animals resume movement before completing the identification.

Figure 4: Preparation of mosquito catch bags to undergo anesthesia. A piece of insulating material is placed between the dry ice and the mosquitoes to avoid freezing of specimens.

7- Morphological identification:

- Material: For morphological identification of mosquitoes, it is required the use of a stereomicroscope with a strong light source (Figure 5), preferably a cold light. This stereomicroscope should have a total magnification between 20X and 60X. Digital microscopes can be an alternative, but they usually have lower resolution. It is also necessary to have a basic dissection kit that includes at least fine-tipped and blunt-tipped forceps for handling the mosquitoes.
- Preparation of specimens for identification: Transfer the mosquitoes, along with the identification label inside the catching bag, to a sterile Petri plate. It is recommended to place absorbent bench paper underneath the dish to facilitate specimen recovery. This process should be performed as quickly as possible to minimize exposure to ambient temperature.

Figure 5: Example of stereomicroscope for mosquito identification. The picture also shows a polystyrene tray that can be filled with ice in order to maintain the cold anesthesia during identification.

- Cold chain and handling of samples: Maintaining the cold chain is essential to ensure that the anesthesia remains effective during the identification process. To do so, you can use a tray filled with ice or, if the stereomicroscopy is high enough to allow proper focus, a chill table. Depending on the day and place of trapping, the catch bag may be filled with hundreds of mosquitoes. In those cases, it is recommended to divide the content of the bag in different Petri plates. This will allow to work in smaller groups of mosquitoes, ensuring that all mosquitoes are exposed to the cold and the anesthesia does not lose effect during the identification process. When doing so, it is important to identify every Petri plate with the date and place of the capture to identify all plates belonging to the same trap.
 - Morphological identification: Species and sex of each specimen must be determined through the use of morphological identification keys such as the software MoskeyTool (Gunay et al., 2018) or the identification key by (Becker et al., 2020). During the identification process, gravid and blood-fed females must be identified and separated from the rest of the samples, to prevent vertebrate host DNA from interfering with genomic sequencing of the mosquito.
- 8- **Preservation of specimens:** Immediately after identification, each mosquito must be individually placed into a labelled RNase and DNase-free microcentrifuge tube. The tube must be placed back in the dry ice. This time, place it directly on

the ice, as the goal is to freeze and preserve the specimen for the long term. Each tube must carry a unique identification code. Tubes must be labeled prior to mosquito identification, in order to avoid manipulating the tube once the mosquito is inside. It is recommended to place the identification code both on the cap and the side of the tube, to prevent misidentification in case of one of the labels being erased. Ideally, the code on the side should be printed on a sticker, so it does not fade over time. Then, place a piece of adhesive tape over that sticker, since the stickers can peel off in the low temperatures of the deep-freezer. The code on the cap should be written with a permanent marker so as not to interfere with the handling of the tube and to remain legible even if the sticker on the side falls off.

- 9- **Long-term storage:** Once all the specimens have been identified, place them in labeled cryogenic freezing boxes and store them at -80°C . To preserve genetic material in optimal condition, freeze-thaw cycles must be avoided. To achieve this, samples should remain inside the deep-freezer until DNA extraction is to be performed.

References

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